

The impact of social media on mental health during imposed social isolation

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has forced legislators, policy makers and governments to impose restrictive measures on their citizens. In turn, people started to experience changes in their mental health by having feelings of social isolation and resorted to spending more time on social media platforms, seeking to maintain and rebuild the lost “social ties”, leading to an increased usage of Social Networking Services (SNS). This research builds on the existing knowledge about SNS usage and mental health by investigating the knowledge gap created by the imposed social isolation and the impact of SNS usage on mental health. A questionnaire answered by 233 respondents revealed a significant positive correlation between compulsive SNS usage and depression, however, it displayed a low significance between the mediator SNS fatigue and the dependent variable (DV), depression. The social isolation has led to an increased effect of Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) and fatigue on the DV.

Keywords

Social Isolation, Mental Health, Social Networking Services Usage, Depression, SNS Fatigue

INTRODUCTION

The last period of time has been filled with uncertainty and the social-economic aspects that govern the world have been influenced by the rapid spread of the new COVID-19 outbreak (Nicola et al., 2020). In response to the accelerated spread of the virus’s bioavailability, governments around the world have been instating restrictions and regulations on both individuals as well as on businesses (Nicola et al., 2020). Social distancing

along with nationwide and even regional lockdowns are only part of the numerous restrictions that attempt to contain the spread of COVID-19 (Nicola et al., 2020). Together with this new set of rules, a plenitude of economic and social consequences has followed: companies operating in the food sectors have financially flourished on average while most of the other sectors have been struggling (Eurostat, 2020).

The status quo has an increasing number of people shifting towards a more digital environment making them work and study remotely. Individuals of all ages have been affected by these restrictions and this situation had people face new challenges, having them adapt to the new ways of living. Research found that rules and restrictions, such as social distancing and lockdowns, paired together with an increasingly digital and remote workstyle, created an increased sense of isolation, loneliness and boredom among people (Banerjee & Rai, 2020). During times of restrictive social interaction rules and lockdowns, social media has been thought to create the “social ties” that are lacking in this period (Banerjee & Rai, 2020). Therefore, with increasingly more socially isolated people in need of creating and maintaining “social ties”, the social networking services/sites (SNS)’ importance has increased.

Moreover, based on literature on psychological wellbeing and social media fatigue, social media platforms such as Facebook, or Snapchat can be referred to as SNS – social networking sites or social networking services (Dhir, Yossatorn, Kaur & Chen, 2018). Therefore, this research will use both social media and SNS interchangeably.

This research has been carried out by means of analyzing both qualitative and quantitative data obtained from primary and secondary sources. The collection of primary data will be done through a 6-point Likert scale questionnaire, while the

secondary data will be addressed through the use of academic literature on subjects such as mental health and social media. Further on in the research a conceptual model including the variables of this study will be illustrated, followed by corresponding tentative statements. The variables presented are SNS usage, SNS fatigue, social isolation, depression, intelligence and manipulation and abuse on SNS platforms. The aim of this paper is to investigate and highlight the relationships between SNS usage and mental health during periods when social isolation is coerced.

Relevance

The topics addressed in this study are especially relevant given the current state of affairs that make SNS, social isolation and depression contemporaneous realities in today's world. Further researching the relationship between SNS usage and mental health during times of social isolation could signal early intervention that could potentially have long-term knock-on benefits (Ellis, Dumas & Forbes, 2020), making this study relevant in the current context and future similar situations of imposed social isolation. Further on in this paper the managerial and academic contribution will be addressed in more detail.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Big tech companies, responsible for supplying people with IT related services and social networking opportunities, have experienced a continued increase of their market share as a result of the forced digital transformation caused by the pandemic (Kshetri, 2020). During this pandemic, when information sharing can be crucial, social media is being increasingly utilized for public risk communication and information gathering, making people more dependent on SNS (Jadhav, 2020). Big tech companies that are invested into social media such as Facebook, have reported an overall increase in the use of their platforms during this pandemic and have signaled a spike in usage in the countries hardest hit by the virus (Schultz & Parikh, 2020), furthermore strengthening their role within the context of this pandemic.

A report of the Pew Research, surveying American adults over the age of 18 revealed that young adults are still the most likely group to use social media (Perrin, 2020). The report reveals that 90% of people aged 18-29 use social media, while 77% of people aged 30-49 use social media (Perrin, 2020). The report is congruent with other studies and reports on this topic and reveals that past a certain age, the increase in age negatively influences the usage of social media (Statista, 2020; Perrin, 2020). Having such a large portion of the internet users exposed to social media, creates

opportunities for further investigation using people over 18 as the target group of this research.

In general, research depicts that the benefits of SNS are contributing to a higher delivery of education, facilitating supportive relationships, forming and promoting identity and self-esteem and providing "social ties" (Collin, Rahilly, Richardson, & Third, 2011). During times of crisis, social media is vital to update on events and scenarios as well as to control people's emotions, stress and fear (Jadhav, 2020). Despite all its possibilities and usefulness, studies indicate that SNS could possibly negatively impact the mental health of its users. Evidence linking social media exposure with low self-esteem, anxiety and depression has been revealed in the works of (Dhir, Yossatorn, Kaur & Chen, 2018; Verduyn, Ybarra, Rsibois, Jonides, & Kross, 2017; Woods & Scott, 2016). Moreover, these mental health issues, especially during adolescence, have been defined worldwide as major public health concerns (Kelly, Zilanawala, Booker & Sacker, 2018).

Research has pointed out that adolescence can be described as a period of high risk and vulnerability for the development of depression, making adolescents with mental health problems more prone to further develop poor mental health throughout their lives (Kessler et al., 2007). Furthermore, the work of Lenhart & Page mentions adolescents as the primary users of social media platforms (Lenhart & Page, 2015). Making this focus group highly represented in academia. Notwithstanding adolescents are most vulnerable for developing mental illnesses, adults (18 and above) are still likely to develop similar mental health illnesses. Resulting in a target group consisting of people aged 18 and above.

Research Questions

The increased exposure and reliance on social media, as a result of COVID-19, has set the grounds for investigating a possible knowledge gap, namely the impact of SNS usage on mental wellbeing as a result of the transformation of social media usage (Gao et al., 2020). The status quo together with the evidence provided by preliminary research has identified a knowledge gap which aims to be resolved by the following research question:

"To what degree does SNS usage influence depression as a result of forced social isolation proxied by SNS Fatigue for individuals that are over 18 years old?"

In attempting to answer the main research question a series of sub-research questions, aiming at concretizing the findings of this paper, will be presented. These sub-research questions are tightly

related to the conceptual model defined in figure 1. Answering them will serve to elucidate the main research question.

RQ1) To what degree does SNS usage lead to SNS fatigue?

- RQ1.1) To what degree do people use SNS compulsively?
- RQ1.2) To what degree do people use SNS as a result of fear of missing out (FoMO)?

RQ2) How does social isolation influence the relationship between SNS usage and SNS fatigue?

RQ3) How does the SNS fatigue link to depression?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

As SNS become a greater part of our lives, compulsive use of SNS is turning into an increasingly prominent concern (Benson, Hand & Hartshorne, 2019). Compulsive usage is defined as an abnormality in controlling behavioral consumptions where an individual is unable to rationally manage his/her routine performances. Compulsive usage is related to impulsive, unregulated thoughts about the use of SNS that are out of the user's control (Benson, Hand & Hartshorne, 2019; Dhir, Yossatorn, Kaur & Chen, 2018). Previous studies have linked compulsive usage with various mental health problems, such as anxiety and depression (Dhir, Yossatorn, Kaur & Chen, 2018). Furthermore, fatigue has been described by research as a consequence of compulsive SNS usage and it is likely that compulsive SNS usage will influence SNS fatigue (Lin, Tsai, Chen & Koo, 2013).

Not only the compulsive usage of SNS but also the fear of missing out (FoMO) is known to be associated with a decrease in emotional well-being of people (Fabris, Merango, Longobardi & Settanni, 2020). FoMO is defined as a concern of being disconnected, absent or missing out on an experience which others have (Dhir, Yossatorn, Kaur & Chen, 2018). Several studies have proven that social network users with a high FoMO are likely to spend more time on SNS and suffer from depression and negative emotions (Baker, Krieger & LeRoy, 2016). Therefore, it is likely that a high level of FoMO could trigger SNS fatigue.

According to research, mental illnesses like depression or anxiety are associated with day-to-day activities such as eating and sleeping, but also with loss of concentration and fatigue (National Institute of Mental Health, 2016). Other research depicts that fatigue is one of the most common symptoms of depression, being a significantly represented attribute compared to

non-depressed people (Drayer, et al., 2006). Compulsive usage of SNS results in social media fatigue (Karapanos, Teixeira, & Gouveia, 2016). Multiple studies suggest that intensive exposure to SNS, whether on smartphone, desktop or SNS platform, results in fatigue and eventually in depression (Hussain, Griffiths, & Sheffield, 2017; Scherr & Brunet, 2017). Based on these studies it is likely that users who experience SNS fatigue tend to suffer from depression when extensive usage of SNS occurs.

As exemplified in the presented conceptual model (figure 1), the relation between SNS usage and SNS fatigue is moderated by social isolation. Social isolation refers to a lack of personal relationships. It indicates a person's subjective feeling of being disconnected from society or other people (Choi & Noh, 2019). During disasters such as COVID-19 and the imposed restrictions, social isolation occurs more often. Studies have shown that SNS usage can help decrease social isolation (Choi & Noh, 2019). According to previous research, the use of SNS could result in social media fatigue and the degree of fatigue mediates depression. Hence, SNS fatigue operates as a mediator between SNS usage and depression (figure 1).

The intelligence quotient(IQ) and emotional quotient(EQ) both function within this study as control variables for the characteristics of depression. A lower IQ score is associated with an increased risk for severe depression and other mental health (Zammit, et al., 2004). Therefore IQ can be a detached factor for developing depression. Similarly, emotionally perceptive people appear to be more affected, resulting in higher extents of depression (Ciarrochi, Deane, & Anderson, 2002). Both quotients describe the capabilities of whether a person can utilize his or her intelligence to be or not to be resistant to developing mental-health issues.

Within the frame of SNS, a factor that can result in depression, but is described as a control variable, is manipulation and abuse on SNS. This variable describes the usage of misinformation and exposure to harassment or cyberbullying (Ferrara, 2015). Studies have shown that victims of this manipulation and abuse develop negative mental feelings which can result in depression (Hussain, Griffiths, & Sheffield, 2017). However manipulation and abuse on SNS are not directly associated with the focus of this research ('compulsive SNS usage' and 'Fear of missing out'), and therefore described only as control variables.

Consequently, with the aforementioned knowledge the following hypotheses are drawn:

H1) SNS usage has a positive relationship with SNS fatigue.

- H1a) Compulsive SNS usage has a positive relationship with SNS fatigue.
- H1b) FoMO has a positive relationship with SNS fatigue.

H2) SNS Fatigue has a positive relationship with depression.

H3) Social isolation affects the relationship between SNS Usage and SNS Fatigue positively.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

RESEARCH DESIGN

The nature of this study, paired with various constraints related to scarcity of time and resources, creates limited opportunities for choosing research strategies. Given the purpose of this research, this paper will be making use of a range of research methods and strategies aimed at providing optimal results given the limitations. Therefore, a mix of primary data and secondary data will be used. The primary data is to be collected via an online questionnaire tool, as a result of the cross-sectional survey research strategy used. The choice for using only a questionnaire as the primary data collection method has been heavily influenced by the above-mentioned constraints and limitations.

Moreover, another reason for using this type of data collection strategy is the personal nature of the measures to be used, making it more suitable to carry survey research (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The observations regarding this research are based on the usage of SNS and on its relationship with depression by individuals. Hence the unit of analysis in this research is people.

The survey questions aim at analyzing the variables presented in the conceptual model through the use of appropriate measures. In this questionnaire off-the-shelf scales have been applied to measure the variables. The dependent variable is being measured on a 6-point likert scale and the design of the questions related to it is based on the World Health Organization(WHO)’s well-being

index, where 6 = ‘All of the time’ and 1 = ‘At no time’ (Psychiatric Research Unit, 1998). The Well-Being index scale is globally recognized and used for variables concerning mental-health (Topp, Østergaard, Søndergaard, & Bech, 2015). A 6-point Likert scale will be applied for the remaining variables in order to prevent neutral answer options (Leung, 2011) as well as to maintain an organized appearance throughout the entire question pool (table 1).

Variable	Measurement items	Reference
Compulsive SNS usage	Q1 I spend free time thinking about SNS or using SNS	(Andreassen, 2015)
	Q2 I feel the urge to use SNS more and more	
	Q3 I use SNS in order to forget about personal problems	
	Q4 I become restless or troubled if I have been prohibited from using SNS	
FoMO	Q1 I fear others have more rewarding experiences than me	(Przybylski, et al., 2013)
	Q2 I fear my friends have more rewarding experiences than me	
	Q3 I get worried when I find out my friends are having fun without me	
SNS Fatigue	Q1 I am likely to receive too much information when I am searching on SNS	(Lian, et al., 2018)
	Q2 I am overwhelmed by the amount of information available on SNS	
	Q3 The amount of information available	

	on SNS makes me tense and overwhelmed	
Depression	Q1 Last 4 weeks I have felt cheerful and in good spirits	(Psychiatric Research Unit, 1998)
	Q2 Last 4 weeks I have felt calm and relaxed	
	Q3 Last 4 weeks I have felt active and vigorous	
	Q4 Last 4 weeks I woke up feeling fresh and rested	
	Q5 Last 4 weeks My daily life has been filled with things that interest me	

Table 1. Measurements

Before conducting the survey, a pretest on at least 11 subjects has been run in order to identify possible errors, optimize the questions and gain early feedback on the design of the questionnaire.

Since the variables will be measured on Likert scales and the Well-Being index, therefore the variables will be treated according to the corresponding scale, namely interval. Therefore a regression analysis will be conducted to explore the relationship between the variables. Within the sampling process, a desired population would comprise people of all ages. However due to the current GDPR regulations, time constraints and scarcity of resources, the target population is represented by all people above the age of 18 that have been exposed to SNS in the last period of time. Moreover, due to restrictions imposed by governments, social isolation has become a reality for many. People seeking the “social ties” that have been lost during this period, end up using social media as a way to connect with others (Banerjee & Rai, 2020). In essence all people subjected to this research, based on the sampling method, are living in areas where social distancing measures have been implemented. Secondary research will be used to identify the degree of social isolation, by acknowledging the restrictions imposed by governments, on our respondents.

A non-probability sampling method - snowball sampling - has been used, resulting in a sampling frame consisting of subjects from within

the researchers’ network. Multiple channels and networks for distributing the survey have been utilized. As per the sample size, (Roscoe, 1975) suggests a number of “rules of thumb” for determining the sample size, of which several have been satisfied in this study, making a sample size between 75 and 500 sufficient for the scope and purpose of this paper. The measurements and the variables used in the questionnaire are based on well-known and well-established scales as previously discussed.

In addition, this research is centered around multi-items variables, resulting in a higher reliability. Although impossible to guarantee perfect non-erroneous submissions, the correctness of the information will be evaluated and any identified errors within the collected data will be accounted for prior to discussing the results. Hence the risk of erroneous information will be reduced. To ensure the validity of the data to be collected, several restrictive rules have been enabled in the design of the questionnaire.

As a result of GDPR regulations, the processing of personal data of minors can be problematic and can require extensive resources - something that is not readily available in this research. Therefore, an age control element has been implemented in the beginning of the questionnaire. Data from people under the age of 18 is therefore not collected. To ensure the privacy of the respondents, all identifiable information collected has been automatically anonymized. No IP address has been recorded and no information about the geographical location of the respondents has been made available.

RESULTS

The results are based on the data collected by the survey, which included 233 respondents. The respondents consisted of 123 males, 95 females and 6 respondents who preferred not to mention their gender. The mean age of the respondents was 34.35 years with a standard deviation of 17.20 and a minimum of 18 and maximum of 120 years old. Compared with females, males reported to have a higher compulsive usage (mean of 4.501 vs 4.337). On the other hand, females reported to have a higher FoMO (mean of 5.407 vs 5.223).

The reliability of the survey measures is calculated using Cronbach's Alpha. Based on the calculated Cronbach's Alpha (table 2), it can be concluded that the items are strongly interrelated and that there is a high reliability.

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of items
Compulsive usage	0.822	4
FoMO	0.822	3
Fatigue	0.847	3
Depression	0.875	5

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha

RQ1. To what degree does SNS usage lead to SNS fatigue?

RQ1.1 To what degree do people use SNS compulsively?

The construct was measured by using the measures mentioned in table 1. The scores on the four measurement items averaged to form the use compulsive index with a high level of internal consistency, M = 4.424, SD = 1.076. A larger number implies more compulsively use, on a scale from 1 to 6.

RQ1.2 To what degree do people use SNS as a result of fear of missing out (FoMO)?

The construct was measured by using the measures mentioned in table 1. The scores on the three measurement items averaged to form the FoMO index with a high level of internal consistency, M = 5.277, SD = 1.032. A larger number implies a higher FoMO, on a scale from 1 to 6.

A multiple linear regression was run to predict fatigue from compulsive usage and FoMO (table 3). Compulsive usage and FoMO statistically significantly predicted fatigue, $F(2, 95) = 15.385, p < 0.000, R^2 = .145$. Both variables added statistically significantly to the prediction, $p < 0.05$. The degree of dependence differs for both variables. One point increase on compulsive usage leads to 0.260 points increase on fatigue, for FoMO this leads to 0.328 points increase on fatigue. $SNS\ fatigue = 1.321 + (0.260 * compulsive\ usage) + (0.328 * FoMO)$. The relationship between SNS usage (the mean of compulsive usage and FoMO) and SNS fatigue is shown visually in figure 2.

Model	B	Std. Error	Sig.
Constant	1.321	.532	.014
Usage	.260	.095	.007
FoMO	.328	.099	.001

Table 3. Coefficients MLR SNS usage - fatigue

Figure 2. Coefficients Scatter plot SNS usage - fatigue

RQ2. How does social isolation influence the relationship between SNS usage and SNS fatigue?

In order to answer this question, the results are compared to similar research prior to the social isolation. According to previous research the relationship between compulsive SNS usage and SNS fatigue has a significance of $p < 0.001$ (which suggests $\beta = .61$). In addition they found that FoMO and SNS fatigue had a significance of $p > .001$ (which suggests $\beta = -.004$) (Dhir, Yossatorn, Kaur & Chen, 2018). The linear regression in this research depicts a significance of $p < .007$ of the relationship between compulsive SNS usage and SNS fatigue (depicting $\beta = .260$). Followed by a significance of $P < .001$ within the relationship of FoMo and SNS fatigue (depicting $\beta = .328$). The data shows that due to the transformation of SNS usage, the relationship between SNS usage and SNS fatigue has indeed changed. Showing a decreased impact of compulsive SNS usage on SNS fatigue and an increased impact of FoMo on SNS fatigue.

RQ3. How does the SNS fatigue link to depression?

A simple linear regression was run to predict

depression from fatigue (table 4). Statistically, fatigue did not significantly predict depression, $F(1, 95) = 3.177, p < 0.076, R^2 = .019$. According to the results of the analysis, one point increase on fatigue leads to -0.109 points increase on the depression variable (structured from depressed 1, to not depressed 6). Depression = $3,655 + -0.109 * SNS$ fatigue. The relationship between SNS fatigue and depression is visualized in figure 3.

Model	B	Std. Error	Sig.
Constant	3.655	.268	.000
Fatigue	-.109	.061	.076

Table 4. Coefficients MLR fatigue - depression

Figure 3. Scatter plot fatigue - depression

Since fatigue does not significantly predict depression, a multiple linear regression was run to predict depression from compulsive usage and FoMO, without using the mediator fatigue (table 5). These variables statistically significantly predicted depression, $F(2, 95) = 6.346, p < 0.002, R^2 = .068$. Only compulsive usage added statistically significantly to the prediction, $p < 0.05$. Depression = $4.539 + (-0.246 * compulsive usage) + (-0.047 * FoMO)$.

Model	B	Std. Error	Sig.
Constant	4.539	.452	.000
Usage	-.246	.083	.003
FoMO	-.047	.085	.577

Table 5. Coefficients MLR SNS usage - depression

Figure 4. Results of the main analysis

DISCUSSION

Based on the statistical analysis it can be concluded that there is a strong correlation between SNS usage and depression. Moreover, it has been revealed in this study that most respondents are using SNS compulsively and have a high FoMO. Consistent with other studies, both of these variables seem to have a significant and positive relationship with SNS fatigue. Leading to an acceptance of H1 (H1a and H1b) within this study. When comparing primary to secondary data, a shift in the dynamic of the relationship between SNS usage and SNS fatigue has been observed. Primary data has evidenced a decreased impact of compulsive SNS usage, and an increased impact of FoMO on SNS fatigue. According to this information, it can be concluded that due to social isolation the impact of FoMO on SNS fatigue increased while the impact of compulsive SNS usage decreased. H3 can therefore not be accepted since there is not enough evidence within this study.

Although a positive relationship between fatigue and depression has been observed, the correlation between the two variables proved to be insignificant leading to a rejection of H2 within this study. An increase in fatigue leads to a higher chance of having depression. The correlation between SNS usage (compulsive SNS usage and FoMO) and depression, excluding the mediator fatigue, has been demonstrated to be significant, concluding that compulsive SNS usage adds statistical significance to the correlation.

For a complete overview of the hypotheses, see table 6.

Hypothesis	Reject	Evidence
H1a	No	Yes
H1b	No	Yes
H2	Yes	No
H3	Yes	No

Table 6. Summary hypothesis

The findings of this study have to be seen in the light of some limitations. Since the sampling approach is based on snowball sampling distributed in the researchers' network, there is a high likelihood that most of the respondents are located in the Netherlands. In the fight against Covid-19 the Netherlands applies a "smart lockdown", where social isolation is significantly different compared to other countries. This likelihood affects the generalizability of the outcome. Utilizing the snowball sampling method negatively affects the reliability which in turn lowers the generalizability of this study.

In addition the median age of the collected data is 24, which does not clearly represent the entire population of 18 and above. The survey also generated extreme outcomes of data (f.e respondents of 120 years old which are active on SNS). Therefore, affecting the generalizability negatively once more.

To counter the limitations of generalizability, measures such as "sound logic" based on valid sources, multi-item measurements, valid scales, minimization of falsified data and Cronbach's Alpha are taken. Hence the generalizability, reliability and validity should not be fully questioned. In addition, personal and loaded questions are included in the survey leading to personal bias and a less valid outcome. However, the personal and loaded questions are based on the guidelines of the WHO, aimed at minimizing personal bias. Therefore increasing the reliability of the outcome.

Academic Contribution

The result of this paper contributes to the expansion of the existing knowledge created by previous research on the topics of social media usage, mental health and social isolation, with particular contributions to the relationships

between SNS usage and depression. This study enlarges the body of knowledge of existing literature and presents itself as a base for further research.

Managerial Contribution

SNS platforms, healthcare providers, practitioners and policy makers, could use the results of this study as a tool in further developing sustainable solutions aimed at mitigating mental health issues associated with social media and imposed social isolation. The link between SNS usage and depression, revealed by this research, could be taken into consideration by companies and other entities that want to be (socially) aware of this phenomenon.

Further research

Based on these findings, further research into the mediums used to access SNS could reveal dependencies that were not covered in this study. A parallel between mobile mediums such as smartphones or tablets and more traditional devices such as laptops used to access SNS should be discussed in future studies, since this may lead to different outcomes. Further research that would take into account the limitations of this paper could contribute to the universal knowledge by having an improved generalizability: measuring and accounting for the control variables Intelligence and manipulation and abuse on SNS. For example, further research should be carried in countries with stricter lockdowns and by using more generalizable sampling techniques.

CONCLUSION

Within this cross-sectional survey study, several contributions to the existing body of knowledge have been revealed. SNS has proven to be increasingly more important in the daily lives of people across the globe, especially during social isolation. However not without consequences. This study brings empirical evidence to the effect of SNS usage on people's mental health during instances of social isolation. To conclude, this study has revealed that during forced social isolation, SNS usage has a positive relationship with SNS fatigue, which in turn leads to higher likelihood of having depression, especially in comparison to previous studies carried before widespread social isolation. The quantitative analysis has revealed strong relationships between compulsive SNS usage and depression with equally strong relationship between SNS usage (compulsive SNS usage and FoMO) and SNS fatigue. Therefore, depression as a result of forced social isolation proxied by SNS fatigue, although

not significant, is highly influenced by SNS usage. All in all, in times of social isolation, people tend to spend more time on SNS and therefore increase their chances of developing depression.

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